

New Isoflavones

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In order to elucidate the structure of some isoflavanones, it became necessary to prepare the corresponding isoflavones. The syntheses of these isoflavones and the ketones, from which the former have been obtained by Joshi and Venkataraman's method¹, are recorded in this communication.

(I)

(II)

2,4-Dihydroxy-5-chlorophenyl Benzyl Ketone (I : R = OH; R' = Cl; R'' = H).—AlCl₃ (20 g.) was added gradually to a solution of 4-chlororesorcin (15 g.) in nitrobenzene (50 ml), cooled at 10°. Phenylacetyl chloride (16 g.), diluted with nitrobenzene (10ml), was added dropwise with constant shaking. The reaction mixture was kept at room temperature for 36 hours, decomposed by HCl/ice, and steam distilled. The product crystallised from dilute ethanol in colorless prismatic rods, m.p. 121°, yield 20 g. It developed a violet colour with ferric chloride. (Found: C, 63.81; H, 4.00. C₁₄H₁₁O₃Cl requires C, 64.00; H, 4.19%). The 2,4-DNP crystallised from ethanol as red needles, m.p. 250°. (Found: N, 12.36. C₂₀H₁₅O₅N₃Cl requires N, 12.65%).

6-Chloro-7-hydroxyisoflavone (II: R = OH; R' = Cl; R'' = H) was obtained by reacting ethyl formate with the preceding ketone and crystallised from glacial acetic acid in colorless prisms, m.p. 272°. (Found: C, 65.82; H, 3.30. C₁₅H₉O₃Cl requires C, 66.06; H, 3.30%).

The acetyl derivative crystallised in colorless prismatic rods from glacial acetic acid, m.p. 190°. (Found: C, 65.00; H, 3.80. C₁₇H₁₁O₄Cl requires C, 64.86; H, 3.49%).

The methyl ether crystallised from ethanol as colorless needles, m.p. 206°. (Found: C, 67.21; H, 4.00. C₁₆H₁₁O₃Cl requires C, 67.01; H, 3.83%).

2,4-Dihydroxy-5-bromophenyl benzyl ketone (I: R = OH; R' = Br; R'' = H), previously prepared by Bhumagra *et al*². (m. p. 103°), was obtained in a much better yield by application of the Friedel-Crafts reaction to a mixture of 4-bromoresorcin and phenylacetyl chloride in presence of AlCl₃, using nitrobenzene as the solvent. It crystallised as colorless needles from dilute ethanol, m.p. 112°, undepressed on admixture with a specimen prepared

1. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 513.

2. *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1947, 25A, 322.

by the method of Bhungara *et al.*². (Found: C, 54.52; H, 3.34. Calc. for $C_{14}H_{11}O_3Br$: C, 54.72; H, 3.58%). It showed a violet colour with ferric chloride. The 2,4-DNP crystallised from ethanol as red crystals, m.p. 257°. (Found: N, 11.21. $C_{20}H_{15}O_6N_4Br$ requires N, 11.49%).

6-Bromo-7-hydroxyisoflavone (II: R = OH; R' = Br; R'' = H), obtained by reacting ethyl formate with the above ketone, crystallised from glacial acetic acid in rectangular plates, m.p. 290°; λ_{max}^{EtOH} 248 m μ , 350 m μ . (Found: C, 56.80; H, 3.01. $C_{15}H_{13}O_3Br$ requires C, 56.78; H, 2.83%). IR spectra (nujol): 3100 cm^{-1} , 1610 cm^{-1} , 1560 cm^{-1} , 1540 cm^{-1} , 1325 cm^{-1} , 1255 cm^{-1} , 1125 cm^{-1} , 1050 cm^{-1} , 930 cm^{-1} , 910 cm^{-1} , 895 cm^{-1} , 855 cm^{-1} , 705 cm^{-1} .

The acetyl derivative crystallised as colorless needles from glacial acetic acid, m.p. 206°. (Found: C, 57.00; H, 3.31. $C_{17}H_{11}O_4Br$ requires C, 56.82; H, 3.06%).

The methyl ether crystallised as colorless rectangular plates, m.p. 186° (mixed m.p. with the sample prepared by the method of Ray and Ray³). (Found: C, 57.63. H, 3.41. Calc. for $C_{16}H_{11}O_3Br$: C, 58.00; H, 3.32%).

2-Hydroxy-4-methyl-5-chlorophenyl benzyl ketone (I: R = Me; R' = Cl; R'' = H), obtained similarly as the preceding ketone from 2-chloro-5-hydroxytoluene, was crystallised from dilute ethanol in prismatic rods, m.p. 112°. (Found: C, 69.01; H, 4.75. $C_{17}H_{13}O_2Cl$ requires C, 69.09; H, 4.99%). It showed a violet colour with $FeCl_3$. The 2,4-DNP crystallised from ethanol-benzene as reddish brown crystals, m.p. 256°. (Found: N, 12.51. $C_{21}H_{17}O_5N_4Cl$ requires N, 12.71%).

6-Chloro-7-methylisoflavone (II: R = Me; R' = Cl; R'' = H), obtained as usual from the preceding ketone, crystallised from acetic acid in colorless needles, m.p. 192°; λ_{max}^{EtOH} 257 m μ , 337 m μ . (Found: C, 70.64; H, 4.11. $C_{16}H_{11}O_2Cl$ requires C, 70.97; H, 4.06%). IR (nujol): 1630 cm^{-1} , 1350 cm^{-1} , 1245 cm^{-1} , 1225 cm^{-1} , 1125 cm^{-1} , 920 cm^{-1} , 895 cm^{-1} .

2,4-Dihydroxy-6-methylphenyl benzyl ketone (I: R = OH; R' = H; R'' = Me), obtained as usual from orcinol, was crystallised from dilute ethanol as colorless needles, m.p. 148°. (Found: C, 74.01; H, 6.00. $C_{15}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 74.38; H, 5.78%). It developed a violet colour with $FeCl_3$. The 2,4-DNP crystallised from ethanol as bright brown needles, m.p. 205°. (Found: N, 13.00. $C_{21}H_{16}O_6N_4$ requires N, 13.27%).

5-Methyl-7-hydroxyisoflavone (II: R = OH; R' = H; R'' = Me), obtained as usual from the preceding ketone, was crystallised from glacial acetic acid as colorless needles, m.p. 241°. (Found: C, 76.29; H, 4.87. $C_{16}H_{12}O_3$ requires C, 76.19; H, 4.76%). The acetyl derivative crystallised from ethanol as colorless rectangular plates, m.p. 128°. (Found: C, 73.40; H, 4.55. $C_{18}H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 73.80; H, 4.76%).

The authors are indebted to Prof. D. Chakravarti, D.Sc., F.N.I. for guidance throughout the progress of the work. Their thanks are also due to Mr. Sukhomoy Chakravarti for his valuable help and to Mr. R. N. Chakravarti for the microanalyses of the samples.